
Changing Role of Libraries: Nep 2020

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Abstract:

The present paper attempts to determine the National education policy 2020 and role of library and information centres. However, these prospects have not been revealed clearly in NEP. However, libraries with quality collection digital resources must communicate quality education. According to NEP 2020, several educational levels will be introduced, including fundamental education, preparatory education, middle education, secondary education, under-graduation, post-graduation education stage, Research Stage and Lifelong learning stage. NEP has emphasized the significance of libraries in a number of areas, including the preservation of national heritage and the promotion of reading culture. Additionally, through practicing fixed librarianship, library professionals must identify new areas in which they can improve and increase the effect of higher education scholars. The author of this review talked about how the government and universities are changing their roles in libraries for NEP. The paper states that the management libraries in the higher education sector must be established as centres for student and research support as well as play a custodial role.

Keyword: National education Policy 2020, Library, Role of Libraries, NEP, Higher Education.

Introduction:

The future of each country is depends on its education system. Implementing education system based on learning methodology is very helpful for every student. They get the good learning environment to flourish. Education is basic right of every person of the country and whole world. Government should facilitate learning opportunities for the people. The world is changes in each field. These changes are very important to achieve the progress. After 34 years, the Union Cabinet finally approved the new National Education Policy. [3,33] There have been

radical changes in the structure of school and higher education and the importance of the 10th and 12th boards is now going to decrease. School education is structured as 5+3+3+4 instead of 10+2. Vocational education will now also be provided after 6th standard; so education in mother tongue till 5th standard will be preferred. Both forms of education have been taken out of the disciplinary framework and made interdisciplinary and coordinated. One can complete higher education by taking both engineering and music simultaneously. [4] Union Human Resource Development scientific approach

will be developed among the school students and importance has been given to provide skills required for 21st century. Here it is important to understand the role of libraries to improve the attractiveness and quality of books available in all languages of country. For effective and efficient library service there must be well funding schemes are necessary for the development of libraries. Digitization and Automation of library services also play a vital role to expand the knowledge throw ought the world. Integration and collaboration in between educational institution and libraries brings a change in dissemination of library services. Understanding the role of libraries for the progress of educational system is must.

Objectives:

The present paper has following objectives.

1. To give brief information of National Education Policy 2020.
2. To describe the Changing role of libraries in National Education Policy 2020.

Vision of National Education Policy:

The National Education Policy 2020 has a vision of creating an India-centric education system that directly contributes to transforming our nation into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society sustainably. The policy aims to achieve this by providing high-quality education to all individuals. A primary objective of the policy is to increase state expenditure on education from around 4% to 6% of the GDP.

New Education Policy 2020:

According to the New Education Policy 2020, the National Education Commission will be the apex body of the education sector and will be chaired by the Prime Minister. The quality of Indian students is good, but due to the lack of research in India, this quality does not benefit India, in fact, due to lack of opportunities for their knowledge and skills, such talented students leave India and look for jobs in other countries. Recognizing the quality of Indians, India is using the talent of other countries for their development by giving good paying jobs to such meritorious students just as a servant. If this quality is to be beneficial for the country, such meritorious students should be given the opportunity to work in the country according to their quality. Big companies like Facebook, Google & Amazon need to start in our country, for that it is very important to give more emphasis on research. Compared to other countries, India's research is minimal.

From the lowest level to the highest level of the society, the maximum feedback has been given to meet the knowledge needs of students of all levels and finally, it seems that the development of the country will be done in a proper way. Therefore, it cannot be said that a particular level has been given more attention or no level has been considered. As per the previous policy, due to the difference between the education given to the students and the interest of the students, there were difficulties in carrying out the study-teaching process effectively, so how can the students be imparted with the knowledge of the subject of interest, art and skill, the students themselves will happily

participate in acquiring that knowledge. As it is designed, surely the student will not only acquire knowledge to get the degree but he will also participate in the process himself as he will get knowledge about the subject of his interest. According to the thought of Mahatma Gandhi, emphasis has been placed on industrial education.[6,31] A student comes out of the education process whether he gets a job or not but with the skills he possesses he will be able to lead his own life properly. In earlier policy 10+2 phase was adopted as per new policy 5 3 3 4 phase was adopted. In short, the state government is going to give serious attention to the education of the students for 12 years as per the previous policy and 15 years as per the new policy. The New Education Policy 2020 recommends that 6 percent of India's GDP should be on education, which is the highest compared to the Commission till date. At present, the percentage of higher education students is 26.3 percent and according to the new the commission has set a target of taking it to 50 percent by the year 2035. According to the RTE Act 2009, free and compulsory education was provided to students in the age group of 6 to 14 years, but as per the New Education Policy 2020, provision has been made special attention in the education of children in the age group of 3 to 18 years. [27,] As part of NEP 2020, various educational levels will be introduced.

1.Fundamental Education stage (Age group 3-8 Yrs.):

Fundamental Education (Age group 3-8 Yrs.)

Education Class	Age
Nursery	4 year
Junior KG	5 year
Senior KG	6 year
First Standard	7 year
Second Standard	8 year

A child's brain grows from 3 years to 6 years. During this period, the child is learning many new things, so the 3-year-old child is included in the education stream, but at the age, the aim is to give them knowledge through various games of interest, without giving them book education in any way. Three years of pre-primary and a total of 5 years of clay 1 and 2, children will be interested in school. In this phase, children will not have kind of examination, but children of this age will gain knowledge of many things through observation.

2.Preparatory Education stage (Age group 9-11 Yrs.):

Preparatory Education (Age group 9-11 Yrs.)

Education Class	Age
Third Standard	9 year
Fourth Standard	10 year
Fifth Standard	11 year

The second phase of the New Education Policy 2020 will be for three years, i.e. in the third, fourth and fifth classes, children will be educated through various activities and the examinations will start from this phase. The medium of

examination will be mother tongue. According to the psychological principle that the student's thoughts can be accelerated through the mother tongue, education through the mother tongue is emphasized. [27]

3. Middle Education stage (Age group 12-14 Yrs.):

Middle Education (Age group 12-14 Yrs.)

Education Class	Age
Sixth Standard	12 year
Seven Standard	13 year
Eighth Standard	14 year

In the subsequent 3-year phase i.e. sixth, seventh and eighth, students are emphasized on vocational courses, Indian language education. In this phase, children will have the freedom to pursue any education in art, skill & sports field according to their interest so that the student will happily participate in the learning process and this phase will create a way of life for him in terms of his future life.

4. Secondary Education stage (Age group 15-18 Yrs.):

Secondary Education (Age group 15-18 Yrs.):

Education Class	Age
Ninth Standard	15 year
Tenth Standard	16 year
Eleventh Standard	17 year
Twelfth Standard	18 year

This is known as the last phase in New Education Policy 2020. Its duration is four years Le Class IX, X, XI and XII. The Board Exam in class 10th and 12th is not in this place but the semester study method has been adopted so that the students do not feel

the importance of studying only for the exam, which will reduce the number of children who study only for some time in the year as it is an annual exam and due to the semester pattern, children will pay attention to their studies frequently. At this stage children are given the freedom learn foreign languages. The format of the exam will be based on critical thinking. Students have freedom of choice of subject.

5. Under-graduation Education Level:

Every subject will have three or four-year undergraduate degrees that can be completed in a number of ways, such as with a certificate after the first year, a diploma after the second year, or a bachelor's degree after the third year of study. It is recommended to follow a four-year undergraduate plan that includes a major, minor, and research projects. [2, 1]

6. Post-graduation Education Level:

One more year of study after graduation will be called Graduate Research. After completing each stage, students will get credits as per present Grades and these students will be able to view the Academic Bank of Credit (ABC) of UGC. You can use these credits to get a job or for further education. The duration of postgraduate studies will be 1 or 2 years. 2 years duration if the student wants to pursue Post Graduation after Graduation and 1 year duration for Post Graduate after Research. [2] For students with a four-year bachelor's degree, the master's degree can be earned in one year; for students with a three-year bachelor's degree, it can be earned in two years; and for students with an integrated five-year degree, the emphasis of the last year is on good research. [30] The Masters degree will contain a sizable research

component to enhance professional competence and prepare students for a research degree.

7. Research Stage:

The Ph.D. research stage requires carrying out good research for a minimum of three to four years for full-time study and separately for part-time study in any core subject, multidisciplinary subject, or interdisciplinary subject. They should take part in an 8-credit course in pedagogy, education, or teaching that relates to their selected Ph.D. field. The prior MPhil programme of one year has been discontinued. [2, 25]

8. Lifelong Learning:

The NEP 2020 promotes lifelong learning and research to avoid individuals with disabilities losing the knowledge, skills, and experience necessary to lead pleasant lives in society. At any stage of life, education and research are thought to foster greater maturity and life happiness. [2]

Significant Highlights of the Policy:

Following are the important significant highlights of the education policy.

1. The system includes 5 + 3 + 3 + 4.
2. The school from 3 years
3. Promoting the libraries
4. Regional or mother-language teaching up to fifth class
5. The founding of BAL BAVANS
6. College affiliation will gradually disappear in 15 years.
7. Foreign universities in India
8. Common Entrance Exam
9. National Education Technology Forum:
10. Academic Bank of Credits

1. 11 Multiple points of entry and exit in higher education
11. Changes in Report Card
12. By 2030, the minimum degree qualification
13. Easing of board exam.

The Changing Role of Libraries in National Education Policy:

The NEP recognizes the role of libraries in education and states that they are essential for promoting reading, providing access to information, and fostering critical thinking skills. The policy recognizes that libraries can serve as centers for learning and research providing access to a wide range of resources, including books, journals, and digital media the reading materials needs to developed in all regional languages with standardized content. The Government as well as Private sector institutions should work together to improve the quality of the materials. The NEP also highlights the importance of school libraries in promoting literacy and language development among children. It recommends that every school should have a library with a collection of age-appropriate books and resources to support students learning. The policy also calls for the development of digital libraries, which can provide access to a wide range of educational resources to students in remote areas.[11, 22]

1. Libraries and Teacher Education:

The NEP also recognizes the role of libraries in teacher education. It recommends that all teacher education institutions should have a well-stocked library with access to digital resources. This will enable trainee teachers to access the

latest research in education and develop their teaching skills. The policy also recommends that teacher education institutions should promote the use of libraries among their students. This can be achieved by integrating library use into the curriculum and providing training on how to access and use library resources. The books should be available in school/ public libraries and make an accessible to all types of students including special child. The reading habit should be promoted across all grades and types of students by using various facilities like, book fair, events, exhibitions etc. The application of ICT should be incorporated in school as well as public libraries. The electronic resources should also be developed according to the needs of school and public libraries.[20,21]

2. Libraries and Higher Education:

The NEP recognizes the critical role of libraries in higher education. It recommends that all higher education institutions should have well-equipped libraries with access to digital resources. The policy also calls for the development of research libraries, which can provide access to specialized resources to support research in various fields. The government should provide the proper infrastructure for the adult and lifelong learning process and engage the community learning by providing the best reading materials in the regional format. The NEP also recognizes the need for libraries to play a more significant role in promoting interdisciplinary research. The policy recommends that libraries should work with faculty and researchers to develop interdisciplinary collections that can support research in multiple fields. Academic libraries have always played a

crucial role in education system, providing access to knowledge, resources, and information.[24]The NEP's recommendations on libraries provide a much-needed framework for enhancing the quality of education in India, by ensuring that students have access to well-equipped libraries at all levels of education. Also strengthen the library materials in all form. One of the significant challenges in implementing the NEP's recommendations on libraries is the lack of resources and infrastructure. Many schools and colleges in India lack the necessary resources to set up and maintain libraries. Therefore, the government and education institutions need to prioritize investment in libraries and provide the necessary resources and infrastructure. Another challenge is ensuring that libraries keep pace with the rapidly changing technology Landscape. With the growth of digital media and the internet, libraries must adapt and provide access to digital resources. This requires a significant investment in technology, training, and infrastructure.

3. Libraries As Centers For Research Support:

The NEP also emphasized the value of research at various universities and institutes. It just suggests that libraries be ready with all the necessary services that customers demand. Libraries may undoubtedly support an organization's research efforts to a great extent. The public and institutional libraries frequently provide funds to grassroots innovators and young business owners so they can plan environmentally friendly products and services and create a pool of revolutions.

Every region of the nation should establish some public and institutional libraries as hubs for supporting research to help inventors, aspiring business owners, and other members of the creative economy. Being an investigator requires having the necessary information, the drive to learn more about the subject, and the desire to contribute to the field. By offering high-quality resources with a specific emphasis on reference management and information retrieval, libraries can help researchers achieve their goals faster. In this regard, specialized librarianship might be quite beneficial. [10, 19]

Libraries can take a particular interest in research, among other subjects. We need an isolated research librarian with expertise in reference administration, statistical analysis, open-source technology, research assistance tools, and retrieval methods. The importance of having a research librarian is emphasized in its goals to establish the national research foundation. NIRF will sponsor financing and manage research activities in addition to the conventional research funding organizations. The research librarian can help NIRF uphold its objectivities as a nodal official. Recently, INFLIBNET created the IRINS system to highlight and organize the research projects being conducted by Indian universities and organizations. To improve the value of IRINS, several librarians are working hard as nodal officers to update vidwans profiles. [28] To assist the university in performing its role as a multidisciplinary institution. They must serve as a well-organized repository for reference books and high-caliber textbooks. Since he must understand at

least a little of each topic discipline in order to relate to each subject area, the librarian has been referred to as a teacher. [10, 17]

4. Provide Student Support:

Libraries are essential to the NEP 2020's success since they offer electronic resources like e-books, journals, and serial publications as well as web-based databases.[23] In addition to emphasizing the digitization of existing resources like books, audiotapes, and video, the NEP emphasized the four elements of the educational system: curriculum, pedagogy, ongoing assessment, and student support. The parent institute would be in charge of establishing crucial student support facilities and making sure they had enough resources to improve their capabilities and efficiency.

5. Technology Integration and Use in Libraries:

When it comes with implementing ICT and embracing cutting-edge technology in a range of areas, India has established itself as a global leader. The nation as a whole is now digitally empowered and transitioning to a knowledge economy thanks to the Digital India programmed. When combined with technology, education plays a crucial role in accelerating growth fourfold. Technology and education are directly correlated with one another and mutually beneficial. The gate keeping of these services and meeting of user requests requires qualified and experienced professionals to keep up with the constant speed of technical changes. [14] The usage and integration of technology has advanced pedagogical practices and enhanced many facets of the

educational system. The National Education Technology (NETF) has been established as an autonomous entity inside the NEP to provide a platform for two-way communication on the use and deployment of technology to improve the current teaching and learning techniques. The NETF will assist in decision-making with regard to the creation, use, and administration of technology in education. In order to make data-driven decisions, NETF will use a steady stream of data from multiple sources, working with a varied group of researchers to analyze the data. To address the widening digital divide and its issues, libraries have evolved into hybrid and digital ones and integrated technology-based solutions. By providing access to materials for teaching and learning, then detecting implementations. [10,16]

6. Libraries As A Platform For Lifelong Learning:

Only formal education is available from the institute. When one has received the appropriate education, he or she must expand their horizons. It is effective to use libraries. It never dismisses caste, creed, or sexual orientation as criteria for whether a person is a regular student or not. The libraries have the reading material needed to advance a student's studies. The age range and duration of classroom instruction are set. As a result, libraries have had a significant impact on lifelong learning. The motivation for lifelong learning is influenced by work, experience, passion, and personal ambition.

7. Adequate Library Employees:

From NEP 2020 on, it will be crucial to have adequate library employees on hand to manage the library services for teachers, students, and the general public, as well as

to design suitable career trajectories and CPD for them. Additionally, all currently existing libraries will be strengthened, rural libraries and reading rooms will be established in underserved areas, reading materials in Indian languages will be widely accessible, children's libraries and mobile libraries will be opened, social book clubs will be established across India and across subject areas, and more cooperation between educational institutions and libraries will be encouraged. [7] The policy also states that libraries must stock a sufficient number of high-quality resources for readers from all fields. Additionally, it is stated that there is a lack of suitable space and amenities for libraries in schools and organizations. As a result, efforts are being concentrated on developing a well-organized space with user-friendly resources until 2025 to give libraries a new sort of value for the general public and societies. [10]

8. Infrastructures appropriate for the library include:

To ensure that all interested adults have access to adult education, study, and lifelong learning, appropriate and acceptable infrastructure will be ensured. Using schools, school complexes, and public libraries for adult education classes that are equipped with information communication technology and well-designed, as well as other community engagement and enrichment activities, will be a key initiative in this direction. The efficient use of physical and human resources and the creation of synergy among these five forms of education and beyond will depend on the sharing of infrastructure for school, higher, audit, and vocational education, as well as other

community and volunteer activities. Because of these factors, adult education centers (AECS) may also be a part of other public organizations as HEIS, vocational training facilities, etc.[10,9]

9. Rethinking Libraries for Research and Development:

Research and development as well as enhancing the scholarly communication environment are given top priority under NEP 2020. The NEP includes provisions to promote and advance research and development in fields involving cutting-edge technology like big data analytics, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, and natural language processing. Through reading and referencing services in a variety of diverse fields, libraries play a significant part in encouraging and assisting scholars. Granting access to databases and research portals for the purpose of gathering data as well as literature. By granting users access to resources around-the-clock, virtual and reference librarians have been able to bridge the gap between time and space while also addressing user needs. The old methodologies and methods for storing data and gathering resources are being replaced by cloud-based libraries. This re-imagined method for libraries has a tremendous deal of promise to better serve its users. [10, 34]

Colleges and Universities Library Role:

Following are the some important role of college and universities libraries for the promotion and progress in knowledge.

1. Facilitate the development and execution of educational programmed that equip students with the abilities to thrive or adapt in a

social and economic context that is always changing.

2. It offers and promotes student efficiency and enhances the academic, aesthetic, societal and emotional development of students.
3. It allows the person to achieve spiritual, inspiring and recreational activities via reading. Besides this, a library also plays an important role in education including:
 4. Helping literacy to become permanent.
 5. Enables the individual to develop their full potential and to expand their erspective, involvement and abilities.
 6. It improves literacy and reading habits among children and Young adults.
 7. It also promotes readings amongst the local communities.
 8. It prepares the person to prepare for future including jog search and other works.

1.Policy formulation and Implementation:

The government is responsible for developing policies and implementing them effectively to achieve the objective of the NEP 2020. This includes creating a framework for the implementation of the policy, establishing targets and timelines for achieving the policy objective and providing resources and support to ensure the effective implementation the policy.

2. Funding and Investment:

The government plays a critical role in providing funding and investment to support the implementation of the NEP 2020 This includes increasing public

spending on education, providing funds for infrastructure development, and supporting research and development activities in education.[11]

3. Curriculum Development:

The government is responsible for developing modern and flexible curriculum that is in line with the objectives of the NE 2020. This includes reviewing existing curricula, developing new curricula, and ensuring that the curriculum is aligned with the needs of the 21st century.

4. Teacher Training and Development:

To ensure that teachers have the skills and knowledge required to provide high-quality education, the government plays a crucial role in providing opportunities for training and development. This includes developing a national teacher training programme, supplying teachers with ongoing professional development opportunities, and making sure that instructors are regularly evaluated and trained. [14]

5. Monitoring and Evaluation:

The government is responsible for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of the NEP 2020 to ensure that the policy objectives are being achieved. This includes establishing a framework for monitoring and evaluation, collecting data and feedback from stakeholders, and using the information to improve the implementation of the policy. [18]

Conclusion:

The National Education Policy of India 2020 recognizes the critical role of libraries in education. It calls for the development of well-equipped libraries at all levels of education, including schools,

teacher education institutions, and higher education institutions. The policy recognizes that libraries can serve as centers for learning and research, providing access to a wide range of resources, including books, journals, and digital media. The NEP's recommendations on libraries provide a framework for enhancing the quality of education in India and preparing students for the challenges of the 21st century. The Government should accept the needs of the library staff and appropriate staff has to be fulfilled to provide the better services from libraries. The policy's focus on providing a holistic and multidisciplinary education, universalization of education, flexible and multilingual education, technology-enabled learning, and teacher training and professional development can significantly improve the quality of education in India.

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